

EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT WEIGHT FRACTION AND DISPERSANTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, graphene oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (RGO) are incorporated into polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and epoxy matrices as reinforcements to fabricate four kinds of nanocomposites. Five kinds of weight fractions of GO and RGO are added into matrices to fabricate nanocomposites including 0.5wt%, 1.0 wt%, 1.5 wt%, 2 wt%, and 3 wt%. In addition to exploring effect of reinforcement weight fraction, three kinds of dispersants are included in nanocomposites to enhance dispersion of reinforcements including poly sodium p-styrenesulfonate (PSS), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP)/Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and Na Polycarboxylate (NP). Tensile tests for nanocomposites with and without dispersants are conducted to evaluate their mechanical properties.

The addition of GO and RGO in PVA and epoxy can enhance tensile strengths of both PVA and epoxy. Tensile strengths of GO(3wt%)/PVA, RGO(3wt%)/PVA, and PVA are respectively 86.48MPa, 80.91MPa, and 37.54MPa. For reinforcement weight fraction of 3wt%, strengths of GO/PVA and RGO/PVA nanocomposites are respectively 230% and 210% greater than that of PVA. Tensile strengths of GO(3wt%)/epoxy, RGO(3wt%)/epoxy, and epoxy are respectively 44.24MPa, 52.81MPa, and 25.7MPa. Similarly, strengths of GO(3wt%)/epoxy and RGO(3wt%)/epoxy nanocomposites are respectively 170% and 210% greater than that of epoxy. Among three kinds of dispersants in nanocomposites, dispersibility of reinforcement is different. NP dispersant achieves best dispersibility of RGO in PVA, while PSS dispersant achieves best dispersibility of GO in epoxy. NP(1wt%)/RGO(3wt%)/PVA has higher tensile strength of 95.89MPa than the counterpart without dispersant, and PSS(1wt%)/GO(3wt%)/epoxy has higher tensile strength of 49.14MPa than the counterpart.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nanocomposite materials with nanoscale reinforcements have emerged in the past decades as a promising novel class of materials, which take advantage of greatly increased specific interfacial area, higher attainable loads, controlled interfacial interactions, and higher total compliance. Various graphene materials have very recently emerged as a new class of potential components for advanced nanocomposites with intriguing new opportunities for the integration into polymer matrices. Graphene nanocomposites show not only superior mechanical properties but also impressive functional properties, such as electrical conductivity, unique photonic/optical transportation, anisotropic transport, and low permeability. The most important material characteristics for graphene are [1-4]: the highest elastic modulus of 1 TPa, very high thermal conductivity of $5.1 \times 10^3 \text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, and the highest known intrinsic electrical conductivity of $6 \times 10^5 \text{S m}^{-1}$. It is noteworthy that the thickness of individual graphene sheet of 0.34 nm, which is the thinnest 2D nanofiller known to date [5].

Graphene oxide (GO) is an oxidized graphene-derived products, which can be widely used as an alternative for graphene materials due to its high dispersibility and processibility in aqueous environment [6-8]. GO can be produced from mineral graphite flakes by thermal oxidation method invented by Hummers [9]. The achieved single atomic layers graphene-like material possess high density of epoxy and hydroxyl groups on both sides of the basal carbon plane and carboxyl groups around their edges [10]. Graphene oxide can be reduced to graphene-like structures, named reduced

graphene oxide (RGO), with similar mechanical and conductive properties by chemical, electrochemical, thermal, hydrothermal, and photothermal reducing techniques [11,12].

The fabrication methods control the fine morphology and physical/chemical properties of graphene-based polymer nanocomposites. For various graphene-polymer nanocomposites known to date, the extent of dispersion and exfoliation of graphitic layers is controlled by the applied shear force, temperature, and solvent polarity. Generally, traditional fabrication routines of the nanocomposites include solution-based processing [13] and melt-based processing [14]. Solution processing maximizes filler dispersion in polymer matrix by using pre-suspended single layered graphene sheets. Aqueous or organic solvents can be used to dissolve graphene materials, including GO and RGO. Advantages of this approach include high dispersion efficiency, simple and fast fabrication step, and a high level of control on component behavior; disadvantages include challenges in finding common solvents, toxic solvent utilization, thin-film limitation, difficulties in solvent removal, and common aggregation issues during mixing and solvent evaporation stages [15]. Li et al. [16] proposed a noncovalent functionalization method in which poly sodium p-styrenesulfonate (PSS) was used to solve the aggregation problem. Noncovalent functionalization improved interfacial bonding between the epoxy matrix and graphene, leading to enhanced tensile strength and modulus of resultant nanocomposites. On the other hand, melt-based mixing is a solvent-free process in which applied mechanical shear force distributes the fillers in the polymer matrix using a screw extruder or a blending mixer [14]. This method allows stacked GO or RGO sheets to be exfoliated into a viscous polymer melt by suppressing unfavorable interactions and inducing component dispersion. However, thermal heating and high local mechanical stresses can affect the stability of components, flake shapes, and the reduction state of graphene oxide sheets.

Based on the previous literature review, both graphene-derived products GO and RGO can be used as reinforcements for nanocomposites. However, few experimental evidences have provided to compare their reinforcement effect. This paper is aimed at clarifying effect of reinforcement weight fraction of GO and RGO on polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and epoxy matrices. Three kinds of dispersants are added to the nanocomposites including poly sodium p-styrenesulfonate (PSS), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP)/Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and Na Polycarboxylate (NP). Micro tensile tests are adopted to evaluate mechanical properties of four kinds of nanocomposites with and without addition of dispersants. Correlation between properties and microstructure is analyzed by SEM in order to figure out the failure mechanism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Fabrication of graphene nanocomposites

Graphene oxide (GO) is fabricated by modified Hummers method [9]. First, 10 gram potassium persulfate $K_2S_2O_8$ and 10 gram phosphorus pentoxide P_2O_5 are added to 50 ml sulfuric acid H_2SO_4 and kept stirring to achieve the solvent. Then 12 gram graphite powders are added to the solvent and the solution are heated to 85 °C and stirred for 4.5 hours. The solution is poured into 2 liter deionized water and kept still for 12 hours. The solution is then vacuum filtered by a filter paper with 0.2 μ m pores and followed by dried in oven at 90 °C for 2 hours in order to achieve the pretreated graphite powders. The powders are added to 460 ml H_2SO_4 and the solution is stirred in an ice bath. Later, 60 gram $KMnO_4$ are slowly added to the solution and heated to 35 °C and stirred for 2 hours. Then 920 ml deionized water is slowly added the solution and the temperature has to be kept under 50 °C. The solution is further diluted in 2800 ml deionized water, and then 50 ml 30% concentration H_2O_2 is added. The solution stands still for 24 hours. The solution is initially set in centrifuge by revolution of 6000 rpm for 1 hour to separate solute and solvent. The solute is further purified as GO by the addition of mixture of water and methanol and centrifuge process is repeated for several cycles. To achieve the reduced graphene oxide (RGO), hexamethyl-enetetramine (HMTA) is used as reduction agent. HMTA is added to the water solution of GO, and weight ratio of HMTA to GO is 1.3 to 3.0. The reduced solution is kept stirring at 95 °C for 12 hours without evaporation. By the centrifuge process similar to that of GO, RGO can be successfully achieved.

To fabricate GO/PVA composites, proper amount of graphene oxide is mixed with 12.5 gram PVA powders and 37.5 gram deionized water. The weight fractions of graphene oxide versus PVA are

designed to be 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, and 3 wt%. The composite solution is then put on hot stirrer at 60 °C to stir and degas for 2 hours under a hood. Then the solution is kept still and cooled down. The solution is then used to fabricate thin film composite by doctor blade method. First, the solution is poured on releasing film above a flat glass substrate; then the solution is then coated on the substrate by a doctor blade with film thickness of 600 μm. The composite solution is then cured in an oven at 60 °C for 40 min to achieve the nanocomposite. The procedure to fabricate RGO/PVA, GO/epoxy, RGO/epoxy nanocomposites is similar to that of GO/PVA composites, instead that curing of epoxy is conducted at 70 °C for 60 min. Three kinds of dispersants are added to four kinds of nanocomposites including poly sodium p-styrenesulfonate (PSS), polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP)/Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and Na Polycarboxylate (NP). Weight fraction of dispersants versus matrix are all 1wt% for PSS, SDS, and NP; while 0.1wt% for PVP.

2.2 Tensile testing

The cured thin film nanocomposite is cut as tensile testing specimen with length×width as 50mm×5mm. Tensile testing is conducted by MTS Tytron 250 micro force testing machine. Both ends of the specimen with length of 10 mm are clamped by fixtures that connect to the machine. The actuator of the machine is set up in monotonic type that pulls the specimen by a constant crosshead speed of 6 mm/min until the specimen breakage. During the testing, the associated computer can record force, displacement, and time. Those data are then used to calculate strength of nanocomposites.

2.3 Characterization

Mechanical properties of graphene nanocomposites are closely related to their microstructure. Therefore, in order to clarify reinforcement mechanisms of GO and RGO on PVA and epoxy and effect of dispersants, fracture morphologies of nanocomposites are then carefully examined by SEM. The observation is then correlated with the tensile testing results.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of reinforcement weight fraction

As shown in figure 1, strengths of GO/PVA and RGO/PVA are close when the reinforcement weight fraction is lower than 1.5wt%. However, GO/PVA shows higher strength at higher weight fraction. Strengths for PVA, RGO(3wt%)/PVA, and GO(3wt%)/PVA are respectively 37.54MPa, 80.91MPa, and 86.48MPa, and best strength of GO(3wt%)/PVA is 2.3 times as high as that of PVA. This can explain as follows. The epoxide, hydroxyl, carbonyl, and carboxyl groups on GO (graphene oxide) are all highly polarized with oxygen atom being the negative center [1]. As a result, graphene oxide can bond with various polar polymers, especially polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), through hydrogen bonding networks and polar interactions. Due to the high density of the highly polar functionalities, the interfacial strength of the polymer-graphene nanocomposites with hydrogen bonding network can be very high. Another trend is that both strengths increase with increasing weight fraction of reinforcement (GO or RGO).

Figure 1: Comparison of tensile strengths of GO/PVA with RGO/PVA nanocomposites.

Figure 2 shows comparison of tensile strengths of GO/epoxy with RGO/epoxy nanocomposites. Strengths for epoxy, GO(3wt%)/epoxy and RGO(3wt%)/epoxy are respectively 25.7MPa, 44.24MPa, and 52.81MPa, and highest strength of RGO(3wt%)/epoxy is 2.1 times as high as that of epoxy. Adhesion effect of functional groups of GO on epoxy is not significant such that RGO seems to show better dispersibility and lead to higher strength for five kinds of reinforcement weight fractions. Both strengths also increase with increasing reinforcement weight fraction.

Figure 2: Comparison of tensile strengths of GO/epoxy with RGO/epoxy nanocomposites.

3.2 Effect of dispersants

In figure 3, effect of three kinds of dispersants PSS, PVP/SDS, and NP on strength of GO/epoxy nanocomposites is compared. It can be obvious observed that with PSS dispersant the nanocomposite indicates best strength among all kinds of epoxy composites. GO(3wt%)/ epoxy/PSS shows highest strength of 49.14MPa compared with 44.24MPa of GO(3wt%)/epoxy without the addition of PSS. According to reference [16], the addition of PSS has two effects. First, by FTIR spectra the π - π

interaction on surface of the modified PSS-GO can be verified. π -stacking intermolecular interaction has strength around 8-12 kJ mol⁻¹[1], which is medium among all kinds of interactions. Second, with a thin layer of PSS wrapped on GO, PSS-GO still remains soluble in water up to one week immersion. With above two effects, fracture surface shows that almost no PSS-GO pulled out is observed, indicating good dispersion of graphene and strong interfacial nanofiller-matrix interaction as a result of functionalization.

Figure 3: PSS dispersant showing best dispersibility of GO in epoxy and leading to highest tensile strength of the GO/epoxy/PSS nanocomposite.

Figure 4 shows that NP (Na polycarboxylate) dispersant has best dispersibility of RGO in PVA and leading to highest tensile strength of the RGO/PVA/NP nanocomposite. Similarly with dispersant NP, RGO(3wt%)/PVA/NP shows highest strength of 95.89MPa among all PVA composites, compared with strength 80.91MPa of RGO(3wt%)/PVA without NP. Polycarboxylate copolymers [18] showed good dispersion effect of silica grains in cement and resulted in ultra high strength concrete. The good dispersion mechanism is due to the control of opposite charges of silica surface and cement solution so that single silica grain could be well attracted by the cement. Similar mechanism is likely to occur for RGO in PVA, which leads to better dispersion of RGO and higher strength. Although PVP/SDS dispersant ever showed good dispersion effect of single wall carbon nanotubes (SWNT) in PVA [17], the dispersant could induced aggregation of SWNT ropes during the composite film processing probably due to the scale factor. This reason could also lead to the negative effect in RGO/PVA composite because lower tensile strength of RGO/PVA/PVP/SDS is observed.

Figure 4 NP dispersant showing best dispersibility of RGO in PVA and leading to highest tensile strength of the RGO/PVA/NP nanocomposite

To understand the interfacial interaction and dispersion state of GO, RGO, dispersant-GO, and dispersant-RGO nanofillers in the PVA and epoxy matrices, fractured surfaces of PVA, epoxy, PVA/reinforcements, and epoxy/reinforcements nanocomposites were examined in SEM. As shown in figure 5 for RGO(3wt%)/PVA nanocomposite, a bundle of RGO layers pull-out in the center of the image indicating poor dispersion effect and interfacial bonding. In contrast, in figure 6 few layers of RGO in RGO(3wt%)/PVA/NP nanocomposite are wrapped by PVA indicating better dispersion effect of RGO by addition of NP. With this evidence, best strength of RGO(3wt%)/PVA/NP is 1.18 times as high as that of RGO(3wt%)/PVA.

Figure 5 In RGO(3wt%)/PVA nanocomposite, a bundle of RGO layers pull-out in the center of the image indicating poor dispersion effect

Figure 6 In RGO(3wt%)/PVA/NP nanocomposite, few layers of RGO are wrapped by PVA at the arrow indicating better dispersion effect of RGO by addition of NP

Effect of addition of PSS dispersant on fracture surfaces of composites are compared in figures 7 and 8. For fractured GO(3wt%)/epoxy nanocomposite shown in figure 7, large extent of local brittle fracture surfaces indicating poor interfacial bonding. On the other hand, in figure 8 for GO(3wt%)/epoxy/PSS nanocomposite, in the center region fracture surface seems to be smoother than that in counterpart without PSS addition in figure 7. This shows that a few layers of GO are wrapped by epoxy indicating better interfacial bonding at interface by addition of PSS.

Figure 7 In GO(3wt%)/epoxy nanocomposite, brittle fracture surface indicating poor interfacial bonding

Figure 8 In GO(3wt%)/epoxy/PSS nanocomposite, few layers of GO are wrapped by epoxy indicating better dispersion effect of GO by addition of PSS

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, effect of graphene weight fraction and dispersants on strength of graphene nanocomposites is presented. For GO/PVA and RGO/PVA nanocomposites, both strengths increase with increasing reinforcement weight fraction. Strengths for PVA, RGO(3wt%)/PVA, and GO(3wt%)/PVA are respectively 37.54MPa, 80.91MPa, and 86.48MPa, and highest strength of GO(3wt%)/PVA is 2.3 times as high as that of PVA. Due to the hydrophilicity of GO in PVA solution, there exists hydrogen bonding at GO/PVA interface which enhances the strength of the nanocomposite. Similarly, for GO/epoxy and RGO/epoxy nanocomposites, both strengths increase with increasing reinforcement weight fraction. Strengths for epoxy, GO(3wt%)/epoxy and RGO(3wt%)/epoxy are respectively 25.7MPa, 44.24MPa, and 52.81MPa, and highest strength of RGO(3wt%)/epoxy is 2.1 times as high as that of epoxy.

Three kinds of dispersants PSS, PVP/SDS, and NP show various degrees of dispersibility of graphene reinforcement in the matrix and result in different strengths of nanocomposites. With dispersant NP, RGO(3wt%)/PVA/NP shows best dispersibility among all PVA composites and has highest strength of 95.89MPa, compared with strength 80.91MPa of RGO(3wt%)/PVA without NP. With dispersant PSS, GO(3wt%)/epoxy/PSS shows better strength of 49.14MPa than 44.24MPa of GO(3wt%)/epoxy without the addition of PSS. The enhancement of composite strength by PSS is because noncovalent functionalization on GO improves interfacial bonding between the epoxy matrix and GO.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Hu, D. D. Kulkarni, I. Choi, V. V. Tsukruk "Graphene-polymer nanocomposites for structural and functional applications," *Progress in Polymer Science*, 39 (2014) 1934-1972
- [2] C. Lee, X. Wei, J. W. Kysar, J. Hone, "Measurement of the elastic properties and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene," *Science* 321 (2008) 385-388
- [3] A. A. Balandin, S. Ghosh, W. Bao, I. Calizo, D. Teweldebrhan, F. Miao, C. N. Lau, "Superior thermal conductivity of single-layer graphene," *Nano. Lett.* 8 (2008) 902-907.
- [4] X. Du, I. Skachko, A. Barker, E. Y. Andrei, "Approaching ballistic transport in suspended graphene," *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 3 (2008) 491-495
- [5] M. J. Allen, V. C. Tung, R. B. Kaner, "Honeycomb carbon: a review of graphene," *Chem. Rev.* 110 (2009) 132-145
- [6] C. Li, J. Adamcik, R. Mezzenga, "Biodegradable nanocomposites of amyloid fibrils and graphene with shape-memory and enzyme-sensing properties," *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 7 (2012) 421-427
- [7] O. C. Compton, Z. An, K.W. Putz, B. J. Hong, B. G. Hauser, L. C. Catherine Brinson, S. T. Nguyen, "Additive-free hydrogelation of graphene oxide by ultrasonication," *Carbon* 50 (2012) 3399-3406
- [8] D. Li, M. B. Muller, S. Gilje, R. B. Kaner, G. G. Wallace, "Processable aqueous dispersions of graphene nanosheets," *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 3 (2008) 101-105
- [9] W. S. Hummers, R. E. Offeman, "Preparation of graphitic oxide," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 80 (1958) 1339
- [10] D. R. Dreyer, S. Park, C. W. Bielawski, R. S. Ruoff, "The chemistry of graphene oxide," *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 39 (2010) 228-240
- [11] S. Pei, H. M. Cheng, "The reduction of graphene oxide," *Carbon* 50 (2012) 3210-3228.
- [12] S. Mao, H. Pu, J. Chen, "Graphene oxide and its reduction: modeling and experimental progress," *RSC Advances* 2 (2012) 2643-2662.

- [13] J. Liang, Y. Xu, Y. Huang, L. Zhang, Y. Wang, Y. Ma, F. Li, T. Guo, Y. Chen, "Infrared-triggered actuators from graphene-based nanocomposites," *J. Phys. Chem.* 113 (2009) 9921-9927
- [14] K. Kalaitzidou, H. Fukushima, L. T. Drzal, "A new compounding method for exfoliated graphite-polypropylene nanocomposites with enhanced flexural properties and lower percolation threshold," *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 67 (2007) 2045-2051
- [15] F. Leroux, J. P. Besse, "Polymer intercalated layered double hydroxide: a new emerging class of nanocomposites," *Chem. Mater.* 13 (2001) 3507-3515
- [16] Y. Li, J. Tang, L. Huang, Y. Wang, J. Liu, X. Ge, S. C. Tjong, R. K. Y. Li, L. A. Belfiore, "Facile preparation, characterization and performance of noncovalently functionalized graphene/epoxy nanocomposites with poly (sodium 4-styrenesulfonate)," *Composites: Part A* 68 (2015) 1-9
- [17] X. Zhang, T. Liu, T. V. Sreekumar, S. Kumar, V. C. Moore, R. H. Hauge, and R. E. Smalley, "Poly(vinyl alcohol)/SWNT composite film," *Nano Letters* 3 (2003) 1285-1288
- [18] J. Plank, C. Schroefl, M. Gruber, M. Lesti and R. Sieber, "Effectiveness of polycarboxylate superplasticizers in ultra-high strength concrete: The importance of PCE compatibility with silica fume," *Journal of Advanced Concrete Technology*, 7(2009) 5-12